

THE INFLUENCE OF GERMAN LANGUAGE ON ENGLISH AND THEIR SIMILARITIES

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Abstract.The aim of this article is to analyze the influence of German on English and the similarities between the two languages and to shed light on their grammatical and lexicological similarities with theoretical data and graphs.

Key words: suffixes, Latin, German, novel, expressions, british life, music, literature, abstract, historical references

Introduction

The English language is peppered with words and expressions from all around the globe thanks to centuries of trade. According to a study by the publishers of the Oxford dictionary, some 28% of English words have their origin in Latin and a further 25% in French. In addition, old German, Norse and Dutch have also influenced a quarter of English words and in recent years, we have seen an increase of German words in popular vocabulary.

Analysis.

In fact, there seems to be a Germanic influence in the vernacular of many areas of modern British life. We can see this in the world of food (Hamburger and Frankfurter), in cultural terms, relating in particular to music and literature (Glockenspiel and Leitmotiv) and historical references (Blitzkrieg and Realpolitik) to name a few examples. Some popular words of German origin are more abstract, such as Doppelgänger, Angst and Zeitgeist, and have introduced new concepts as well as words into the English language. German words are also on the increase in the media, a fact that language experts are attributing to the way in which German compound nouns enable the author to neatly sum up the current climate. In fact, the use of the word Schadenfreude defined as the delight at the misfortune of others has seen a 30% increase in its usage in print in the last year! Other words, such as über as an exaggerator, have become fashionable with the blogging community. Using foreign words is a common technique in literary translation, for example the characters in a translation of a German novel may be referred to as Herr and Frau to evoke a sense of foreignness. The Translation People has a network of translators who work both from and into German. Our translators are experts not only in their subject area and language combination, but also in the source and target cultures and therefore know when to use foreign loanwords to really make your text stand out. Therefore, if one search for the real origin of commonly used words, it will be known that .80 of the 100 most common words in English are Germanic in origin. These most basic, most frequently spoken words in English and German are from the same roots, making them all extremely similar. Give or take a few spelling and pronunciation differences, they're practically the same. For example:

I have – Ich habe

It is long – Es ist lang

Where is that – Wo ist das

There are range of words which have same sound.

For instance, the Germanic version of the word 'house' is 'Haus', the Germanic version of the word 'university' is 'Universidad' and the Germanic version of the word 'camera' is 'Kamera'. Even the

German sentence "Ich trinke Wasser" means "I drink water,". Hence it will be fair to conclude that the similarities in word sound between the two languages are endless.

Moreover, these words are also alike in pronunciation;

These are the words which are alike:

Apfel - apple.

Besser - better.

Buch - book.

Bruder - brother.

Delfin - dolphin.

Denken - think.

Essen - eat.

Foto - photo.

Additionally, the suffixes which are used to make degree of comparison are also the same: er, r- used to make comparative degree

est, st- are used to make superlative degree.

For instance,

English

Light-lighter-lightest

German

Alt-alter-altest

In addition, English and German follow very similar syntax (word order) and grammar. Adjectives and adverbs come before nouns in a sentence. Romance languages follow the opposite pattern. For example, English-speakers say "the red car," but in Spanish the phrase could be "el auto rojo" (or, "the car red"). Germans say "rotes auto" for the same phrase. English follows a simple grammatical pattern for its sentence structure. The basics are subject-verb-object. For instance, "The boy runs to the house." (Boy is the subject, runs is the verb, and house is the object.) In German the phrase is "Der junge rennt zum haus." Spanish and other Romance languages follow the same pattern. "El niño corre a la casa." So in this respect, English and Romance languages are the same. It's the adjectives that make the difference in word order here. Akorbi works in more than 170 languages. Our qualified interpreters and translators will provide accurate communication, including proper syntax and grammar.

Conclusion

English naturally evolved, much like any language evolves, when humans move from one part of the world to another. Evolution takes time, and despite 58% of English vocabulary (more than half) coming from Romance languages (Latin and French), linguists still consider English to be a Germanic language to this day because of how the language followed human migration patterns and the grammar of modern English. Akorbi works in German, all of the Romance languages.

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